

Analysis of circular errors

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1 Abstract

This paper investigates the errors of circular system. We provide a proof that the circular system has properties that create errors in the field of geometric mathematic.

We prove that at $\frac{\pi}{2}$ and $\frac{3\pi}{2}$ (90 and 270 degree angles respectively) trigonometric functions encounter mathematical errors.

2 Introduction

The circular system was used in the ancient times to create the most important inventions in human history, even though it has critical flaws in mathematical functioning. These flaws appear when a geometric figure is aligned with the y axis such that the figure has a width of zero units.

3 Proof

Let $\triangle ABC$ be a right triangle placed on a cartesian coordinate system at coordinates $(0,0)$.

Let $a,b,c \in \mathbb{R}^+$ be the sides of the triangle such that $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$.

Let side a be aligned with axis y .

Let side b be aligned with axis x .

Let side c be the hypotenuse of the triangle.

Let $\alpha = 90^\circ$ (vertex **A**), $\beta = 30^\circ$ (vertex **B**), $\gamma = 60^\circ$ (vertex **C**).

Such that:

Figure 1: $\triangle ABC$ on a cartesian coordinate system.

When $|AB|$ is aligned with axis y such that $\alpha = 90^\circ$ then using the circular system properties for 90° we read that:

$\sin \alpha = 1$ and $\cos \alpha = 0$,

substituting the tangents formula: $\tan \alpha = \frac{\sin \alpha}{\cos \alpha}$

we derive that $\tan \alpha = \frac{1}{0}$ which is an obvious mathematical error.

The same error appears at the 270° angle, using circular properties for the 270° angle we read that:

$\sin \alpha = -1$ and $\cos \alpha = 0$, thus

$\tan \alpha = \frac{-1}{0}$ creating the same mathematical error.

See circular system properties here [Trig Cheat Sheet by Paul Dawkins](#)

4 Conclusion

We have provided proof that trigonometric functions encounter mathematical errors at 90 and 270 degree angles and we find that the domain of right triangle that avoids these errors is:

$$D = X \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \left\{ \frac{\pi}{2}, \frac{3\pi}{2} \right\}$$

And we also find that the limit for $\tan \alpha$ should be defined as follows:

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 90^\circ} \tan \alpha = \infty$$